

Trade Liberalization and Agricultural Growth in Africa: A Friend or Foe?

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Abstract

With the aim of assessing the impact that trade liberalization has on agricultural growth as in value added in Africa, the study uses trade openness as a proxy measure of trade liberalization to ascertain whether it has a substantial impact on agricultural value added in Africa. The data for the study were sampled from 1996 to 2017 and were sourced from World Development Indicators and Worldwide Governance Indicators for a panel of 34 African countries. The study's findings confirm that there is an inverse relationship between trade liberalization and agricultural growth in Africa and it also witnessed evidence of bidirectional homogeneous causality between agricultural export performance, trade liberalization, and employment in the agricultural sector, economic growth, government effectiveness and agricultural growth. However, increasing the agricultural export share in Africa could result in agricultural growth. The study used GLS random effects, fixed effects, generalized linear model and multivariate regressions to analyze its data in drawing its conclusion.

Keywords: Trade liberalization; Africa; Agricultural growth; Generalized linear model; Multivariate regression

1. Introduction

Trade policies have now been considered as pertinent in the economic policy making of countries due to globalization. It has been proven that there are significant implications of trade regimes in some evolving economies for economic growth and efficiency (Rodriguez & Rodrick, 2001; Dollar & Kraay, 2000; Edwards, 1998; Krueger, 1997; Sachs & Warner, 1995; Dollar, 1992). Scores of literature have empirically established that the liberalization of trade policies propagated economic growth rapidly through export juxtapose the policies which are protection wise. The argument as to whether the rapid growth of an economy can be characterized by export-driven strategies has been on consensus by prolific economists, but as to whether the tremendous increase in agriculture can be attained through trade liberalization successfully still remains divergent. Meanwhile, a section of the argument posits that the steady growth in agriculture has lately been as a result of the inability to fully comply and complete the “multilateral trade negotiations under the auspices of the Doha Round” (Patrick et al., 2018). The contradictory view from the other section holds the opinion that trade literally does not significantly impact growth by ignoring domestic policies that are most effective. To compare and contrast, these divergent views could be considered as the reasons why trade liberalization in the agriculture sector has not been realized; meanwhile, trade openness is cushioning the industry and services sectors through the removal of restrictions on imports and minimization of discrimination of export policies (Koning & Pinstrup-Anderson, 2007). Potentially, trade liberalization in the agricultural sector can boost agriculture in developing economies because about 70% of the world's poor population is in agriculture (World Bank, 2003). It is also contemplation as to whether developing economies could fairly rack from the impending negotiation, which sought to liberalize trade in agriculture. Prior studies asserted that developing economies that are into food-importing could be affected negatively through the multilateral trade liberalization when the Uruguay Round is implemented (Martin & Winters, 1996; Goldin & Knudsen, 1990). It is evidenced that cash crops from developing economies that are exported could receive a slower growth rate as compared to the prices of products imported into the developing economies from temperate zones.

Agriculture is the main occupation of Sub-Saharan African countries while many depend on the primary products and also export few to a small number of markets abroad (Patrick et al., 2018). Generally, there are enormous prospects in the agriculture sector for Sub-Saharan African countries and the developing economies as a whole. Imbs and Wacziarg (2003) suggest that low concentration in the agricultural sector by not churning out advanced technologies will lead to low productivity and growth (Hausmann et al., 2007). In furtherance to this, diversification is the key to ensure higher productivity to crop more export earnings and pave the way for stability in the macroeconomic foundation. In addition, when countries in the Sub-Saharan African countries adapt to the utilization of modern technologies through diversification into the agro-industry, seemingly, it propagates economic growth, reduces the dependence on primary products and in the long run creates jobs.

Nonetheless, the arguments with regards to trade liberalization and agricultural growth are not direct; some studies posit that there are mixed results; hence trade liberalization benefits developed economies than developing economies. Moreover, there are possible economic downturns that could arise such as food insecurity, rural income inequality or loss of income from agriculture produce and employment in the short and medium-term (Parikh, 2004; Chand, 2002; Chand & Jha, 2001; Nayyar & Sen, 1994; Gulati & Pursell, 1991; Huang & Roselle, 2003:2008; Huang et al., 2003; Li, 2003, Lu, 2000; World Bank, 1991; Lardy, 1986). To be able to understand the implications that trade liberalization has on agricultural production, it is prudent to keenly take into consideration the nexus between trade liberalization and agricultural growth to properly ascertain the linkage. Empirically, it has been established that have liberal policies or strategies on agriculture enjoy vast economic fortunes but it is not openly evident that rapid growth in agriculture can be successfully achieved through liberalization. Even though, it is possible for liberalization in the agricultural sector to promote commercialization of agricultural products and also champion agriculture diversification; it is very critical to fish out the right channels through which agricultural trade liberalization could significantly impact or develop the rural economies of developing economies. On these tenets, the study draws its motivation to carefully assess the impact of trade liberalization on agricultural growth in Africa by considering countries that export agricultural raw materials. Moreover, the assessment of the impact that trade liberalization could have on growth in the agricultural sectors can support the debate on the subject matter which has divergent views. Perhaps, the study could significantly support academic and intellectual discussion as well as policy making directions.

The organization of the study comprises of section 1 which introduces the study and throws more light on the problem of trade liberalization and agricultural growth, section 2 presents the data and methodology of the study, section 3 contains the empirical findings and discussion, and finally, section 4 concludes the study and make some recommendations.

1.1 Trade liberalization and Agricultural growth

Trade, thus, international trade has a significant linkage with economic growth. This relationship could be supported by empirical studies (Michaely, 1977; Balassa, 1978; Dollar, 1992; Sachs & Warner, 1995; Rodriguez & Rodrick, 2001; Dollar & Kraay, 2000). From the studies, they asserted that growth of an economy relies on the constant effort by the country to integrate its local economy into the global economy with regards to the critical issues surrounding international trade and trade liberalization and their significant impact on economic growth (Wacziarg, 2001; Levine & Renelt, 1992; Feder, 1982). In review of these studies, it could be realized that economic growth's impact through trade are mostly as a result of inflows of foreign direct investments, increased in market size, positive effect of external forces, technology transfers, new capital investments, privy to foreign market structure, product quality through international competition, productivity growth from economies of scale.

Many share different views on the linkage between trade liberalization and agricultural growth in India and China (Jha et al., 2005; Chand, 2004; Parikh, 2004; Storm, 2001; Nayyar & Sen, 1994; Pursell & Gulati, 1995;

Huang, Chen, Rozelle, Tuan, 2003; Huang & Chen, 1999; Anderson, 1997). In a study that examined the relationship between trade liberalization and agricultural growth, Surajit (2010) posits that there is a significant causal relationship between trade liberalization and agricultural growth in India and China. Also, Fonchamnyo and Akame (2017) support the debate that trade liberalization significantly impacts agricultural growth as they found that there trade openness through trade liberalization together with value added in the agriculture, propagates the diversification of exports in Sub-Saharan Africa.

Prior study to assess the dependence of trade, trade liberalization and the diversification of exports in developing countries, Patrick et al. (2018) used parametric and non-parametric analyses to unravel the relationship that exists among these variables. In their conclusion, they inferred that trade liberalization through the reduction in import tariffs promotes export diversification which in the long run, promotes economic growth.

2. Data and Methodology

2.1 Data

To be able to achieve the study’s objective, it considered some vital variables to represent the dependent, independent and control variables respectfully. As the study intends to find the impact that trade liberalization has on agricultural growth, trade liberalization is measured by proxy of trade openness thus total trade as a percentage of GDP as the independent variable. However, the dependent variable thus, agricultural growth is also measured by the value added in currency (\$) of all agricultural produce at constant. In addition, to be able to control for the effect that could emerge as a result of trade liberalization, agricultural export share and agricultural export performance are chosen to represent as such and economic growth as well as government effectiveness are also considered to control for the effect of agricultural value added as in growth in the sector. More details about the variables can be found in table 1 below. The study used panel data of 34 African countries from the period of 1996 to 2017. The data were collected from World Development Indicators and Worldwide Governance Indicators.

Table 1 Variable description

Variable name	Description	Measurement
Intradeopen	Trade (% of GDP)- Independent variable	Trade liberalization
Inaggrowth	Agriculture, forestry, and fishing, value added (constant 2010 US\$) Dependent variable	Agricultural growth
Inagexpshare	Agricultural export/total export of goods and services Control variable	Agricultural export share
Inagexppf	Agricultural export/Agricultural production % of GDP Control variable	Agricultural export performance
Inempagric	Employment in agriculture (% of total employmen ILO estimate) control variable	Employment
lngdppc	Gross domestic product per capita (constant 2010) Control variable	Economic growth
goveff	the perception that is held to the extent that policies formulated and implemented by the government with regards to civil and public services delivery: Measured in range; +2.5 means strong, -2.5 means weak.	Government effectiveness

2.2 Methodology

This study is a panel study hence the use of panel data methodologies or approaches such as unit root, correlation matrix, cointegration test, panel gls random effects regression, fixed effects regression, generalized linear model, multivariate regression and homogeneous causality test. The study deems it imperative to employ

these approaches to achieve its objective of ascertaining the true relationship that exists between trade liberalization and agricultural growth and also find out the direction of causality between the independent and dependent variables.

The first approach of the study is to ensure that the variables are stationary, therefore it will perform unit root test to check for evidence of no unit root. However, the tests of Levin et al. (2002), Im et al. (2003) and, Maddala and Wu (1999) are considered due to their capability of checking and correcting the problem of simultaneity, heterogeneity and homogeneity in the sampled data. The null hypothesis for unit root positions that there is unit root in the variables therefore the tests for unit root should either accept or reject the hypothesis; moreover, confirmation of no unit root simplifies that the study's regression will not be termed as spurious. Im et al. (2003) proposed the following equation for the unit root test:

Equation 1

$$y_{it} = \rho_i y_{i,t-1} + \sigma_i x_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

From equation (1), x_{it} stands for the integration of all the descriptive variables; ρ_i stands for the elasticities of the autoregressors, ε_{it} represents the residual term whilst i and t stands for the time period. Im et al. (2003) pave the way for a variety of order of serial correlation (Apergis & Payne, 2010) and following the normal averaging of augmented dickey Fuller (Inglesi-Lotz, 2016) equated as: the equation is adopted from (Maji and Sulaiman, 2019).

Equation 2

$$\varepsilon_{it} = \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \theta_{ij} \varepsilon_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

By putting equation (1) into Equation (2) results the following equation:

Equation 3

$$y_{it} = \rho_i y_{i,t-1} + \sigma_i x_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} + \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \theta_{ij} \varepsilon_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

In equation (3), ρ_i represents the number of lags in the regression of ADF. Evidence of no unit root confirms that the study can continue with the next step of the study which is to check for multicollinearity. The correlation matrix is adopted to function out the problem of multicollinearity and also find out the correlation linkage among the chosen variables. The rule of thumb for correlation matrix posits that no two independent variables should be highly correlated with the dependent variable at the coefficient of $-/+0.70$ or above. After, it has been evidenced that there in multicollinearity then the next is to check for cointegration relationship. This relationship posits that there is a long run equilibrium or linkage between the dependent and the independent variables.

The next step after the cointegration test is to performance the data analysis by using the regression models chosen a suit. The main regression models of the study are gls random effects and fixed effects regression. In order to statistically confirm the results that will be produced by the main models, two other models are chosen to robust check to be able to make a strong statistically conclusion. Lastly, a homogenous causality test (Dumitriscu & Hurlin, 2012) is performed to ascertain the linkage or direction of causality among the variables. There are two expected directions of causality thus either bidirectional or unidirectional causality. Bidirectional causality refers to the causality in which all the two variables involved have an effect on each other and

unidirectional causality refers to the causality in which only the first variable in the causality linkage has an effect on the latter.

Model specification

The econometric model considered for the study is a linear model and can be written as:

$$Agricultural\ growth = f (Trade\ liberalization, economic\ growth, government\ effectiveness, agric\ export\ share, agric\ export\ performance, employment\ in\ the\ agricultural\ sector) \quad (4)$$

$$Y_{it} = \beta_0 + (\beta_1 X_1)_{it} + (\beta_2 X_2)_{it} + \dots + (\beta_k X_k)_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \quad (5)$$

In the equation (5), β_0 represents the coefficient of the intercept, or constant, $\beta_1 X_1$ to $\beta_k X_k$ are the independent and control variables (lntradeopen, lnagexpshare, lnagexppf, lngdppc, goveff, lnempagric) thus predictors or regressors, ϵ represents the error term or disturbances in the model, Y represents the dependent variable (Agricultural growth), i represents the cross-section of 34 countries and t represents the time period from 1996 to 2017. All the variables are in their natural logarithm except government effectiveness (goveff).

3. Empirical findings and discussion

3.1 Descriptive statistics

In table 1, the descriptive statistics of the study’s variables can be found and from the table, it can be reported that Agricultural growth for the period of 1996 to 2017 stood at an annual average rate of 20.81% supporting an economic growth 6.954% annually for 34 African countries sampled for the study. On the other hand, trade liberalization thus trade openness thus total trade over GDP grew annually at 4.067%, while agricultural export share and agricultural export performance were at an annual growth rate of 0.334% and 0.264% respectfully. However, governments' effectiveness in providing public goods and ensuring that civil and public institutions or services worked to the ultimate had a score of -0.547 which is somewhat poor on the average in the sample period. Furthermore, employment in the agricultural sector grew at an average annual rate of 3.762% from 1996 to 2017. Notable, the standard deviations of the variables are homogeneously related.

Table 2 Descriptive statistics

	lnagricgrowth	lnagxshare	lnagexppf	Intradeopen	lnempagric	lngdppc	goveff
Mean	20.808	0.334	0.264	4.067	3.762	6.954	-0.547
Median	21.393	0.415	0.430	4.064	3.909	6.692	-0.572
Maximum	25.462	2.085	1.668	4.989	4.528	9.386	1.049
Minimum	0.000	-2.985	-6.100	2.882	1.526	5.346	-1.884
Std. Dev.	3.973	0.726	0.879	0.395	0.644	0.988	0.593
Observations	748	748	748	748	748	748	748

All the variables are in their natural logarithm except government effectiveness.

3.2 Panel unit root test

In order not to run a useless (spurious) regression, the study employed four-unit root tests to unravel the stationary status of the variables to reject the null hypothesis which posits that none of the variables are stationary hence have a unit root. Table 3 displays the outcome of the unit root test performed; it is evidenced that at level form lnagexppf, lnagexpshare and goveff were stationary in the all the four tests performed. However, lnaggrowth, lntradeopen, lngdppc and lnempagric were stationary in only the LLC test. Subsequently, the tests were done in the first difference and at first difference, all the variables became stationary in all the four tests performed at a 1% significance level. Therefore, the study can confirm that at first difference, all the variables are stationary, hence the rejection of the null hypothesis.

Table 3 unit root tests

	LLC	IPS	ADF-Fisher	PP-Fisher
Level form				
lnaggrowth	-2.959**	2.010	58.096	79.954
lnagexppf	-5.416***	-4.774***	133.138***	130.310***
lnagexpshare	-4.147***	-3.624***	113.308***	125.535***
lntradeopen	-1.821**	-1.243	75.324	67.690
goveff	-3.698***	-5.013***	252.219***	487.763***
lngdppc	-3.434***	2.778	64.112	78.377
lnempagric	-1.655**	3.999	47.859	39.470
First difference				
lnaggrowth	-25.009***	-22.217***	501.398***	614.577***
lnagexppf	-23.076***	-22.186***	522.867***	1539.64***
lnagexpshare	-25.410***	-25.564***	595.197***	1453.57***
lntradeopen	-20.114***	-19.471***	438.221***	514.928***
goveff	-92.090***	-79.783***	4998.72***	5524.95***
lngdppc	-13.342***	-13.897***	312.330***	365.034***
lnempagric	-10.237***	-10.816***	263.294***	415.622***

Note: *** indicates 1% significance level, ** indicates 5% significance level. LLC stands for Levin, Lin & Chu test, IPS stands for Im-Pesaran & Shim test, ADF-Fisher and PP-Fisher stand for Maddala & Wu chi square tests. All the variables are in their natural logarithm except government effectiveness.

3.3 Correlation matrix

The problem of multicollinearity is associated with more than two independent variables that have a high correlation coefficient with the dependent variables which are mostly not healthy for empirical study. However, the study intends to check for this problem by employing the use of a correlation matrix. In table 4, the outcome of the correlation matrix computed can be found. According to the result, there is no problem with multicollinearity in the variables because the highest coefficient of the independent variables is -0.145 which is not even closer of ± 0.70 . To account for the correlation linkage between the dependent variable and the independent variables, agricultural export share showed a positive and significant correlation with agricultural growth while agricultural export performance showed positive but was insignificant. Moreover, trade liberalization (trade openness), economic growth and government effectiveness showed a negative and significant correlation with agricultural growth. Meanwhile, employment in the agricultural sector also showed a negative but insignificant correlation.

Table 4 Correlation matrix

Correlation	lnaggrowth	lnagexpshare	lnagexppf	lntradeopen	lnempagric	lngdppc	goveff
Probability							
lnaggrowth	1						
lnagexpshare	0.081**	1					
lnagexppf	0.059	0.861***	1				
lntradeopen	-0.145***	-0.234***	-0.220***	1			
lnempagric	-0.052	0.421***	0.390***	-0.448***	1		
lngdppc	-0.138***	-0.194***	-0.214***	0.239***	-0.147***	1	
goveff	-0.115**	-0.024	-0.135***	0.071**	-0.081**	0.485***	1

Note: *** indicates 1% significance level, ** indicates 5% significance level. All the variables are in their natural logarithm except government effectiveness.

3.4 Cointegration test

Cointegration tests confirm the long run relationship that exists between dependent and independent variables. Also, it is performed to ascertain whether the variables are cointegrated to be able to infer on the regression

analysis that the coefficients that will be produced are long run estimatons. However, the study patronized the tests proposed by Pedroni (2004) and Kao (2000) to confirm the cointegration relationship between the variables. The results of the cointegration tests can be found in table 5. From the outcome, the variables are cointegrated; hence there is a long run relationship between the dependent and the independent variables at 1% and 5% significance level. The seven approaches used by Pedroni confirmed significance in four approaches in both within-dimension and between-dimension. On top of it, the Kao test also confirmed 5% significance.

Table 5 Cointegration tests

Pedroni Cointegration test							
Alternative hypothesis: common AR coefs. (within-dimension)							
	Statistic	Prob.	sig.	Statistic	Prob.	sig.	Weighted
Panel v-Statistic	-1.238	0.892		-2.580	0.995		
Panel rho-Statistic	3.614	1.000		4.403	1.000		
Panel PP-Statistic	-2.605	0.005	**	-3.266	0.001	***	
Panel ADF-Statistic	-2.931	0.002	**	-3.111	0.001	***	
Alternative hypothesis: individual AR coefs. (between-dimension)							
	Statistic	Prob.	sig.				
Group rho-Statistic	6.748	1.000					
Group PP-Statistic	-6.144	0.000	***				
Group ADF-Statistic	-4.388	0.000	***				
Kao Cointegration test							
	t-Statistic	Prob.	sig.				
ADF	-1.824	0.034	**				

Note: *** indicates 1% significance level, ** indicates 5% significance level.

3.5 Assessing the impact of trade liberalization on agricultural growth

The objective of the study is to assess the impact of trade liberalization on agricultural growth in Africa. In pursuit of the objective, the study employed the use of GLS random effects and fixed effects as the main regression methods and multivariate and GLM as the robust check methods. The outcome of the regression analysis can be found in table 6. It can be witnessed in table 6 that trade openness; thus, a proxy measure of trade liberalization, showed a negative and statistically significant impact on agricultural growth in Africa. The relationship is an inverse one which confirms that in the long run, a further increase in trade openness or trade liberalization will lead to a decrease in agricultural growth by 1.893% and 2.175% in fixed effects and random effects respectively. Considering the outcome of the robust check methods, they strongly affirm the outcome of the main methods that there is an inverse relationship between trade openness and agricultural growth. This result signifies that trade in Africa has been unfair where more imports are welcomed than exports which have resulted in this negative relationship between trade and agricultural growth. Moreover, it also implies that most of the imports that come into Africa are mostly agricultural raw materials and products which rarely hamper the growth in the agricultural sector.

However, the increase in agricultural export share could result in an increase in agricultural growth. This assertion is supported by the evidence produced by the outcome of the study's analysis from table 6. In the table, it can be established that a percentage in agricultural export share will lead to an increase in agricultural growth by 0.974% and 0.732% in random and fixed effects approaches respectively, as they are supported by the robust check methods. The performance of agricultural exports has not been promising over the sample period in Africa which could clearly be witnessed in the outcome of the study's analysis. It is evidenced in table 6 that agricultural export performance has an insignificant impact on agricultural growth in Africa hence further increase in the mode of performance could not result in an increase in agricultural growth.

Generally, employment in the agricultural sector could be seen as a prospect for higher productivity but the outcome of the study’s analysis presents a divergent view where it posits that further increase in the employment in the agricultural sector will lead to a decrease in agricultural growth. This confirms that there is an inverse relationship between employment in the agricultural sector and agricultural growth. Obsolete ways of agricultural practices cannot result in higher productivity since we are in the age where technology is taking over the way things are done across the length and breadth of our daily lives. Also, developed countries use advanced technologies in agricultural practices hence the increase in their agricultural growth where most of their produce find their way into African economies. Perhaps, in order to catch up with these countries, then it is advisable for African countries to employ the use of advance technologies to increase their output in order to increase productivity also to increase agricultural growth other than employment that is more of manual labour that cannot yield higher productivity. Economic growth seems not to have any significant impact on agricultural growth but in the fixed effects, there is an inverse relationship between economic growth and agricultural growth. Notably, governments’ effectiveness in Africa with regards to good policies formulation and implementation to ensure the provision of public goods and the effective function of civil and public institutions to effect policies formulated for the efficient and smooth flow of services that could help the sectors flourish in the economy including the agricultural sector are ineffective and also lack transparency and efficiency hence further increase or heightened of such practices will lead to decrease in agricultural growth.

Table 6 Regression results

	1	2	3	4
	GLS random effects	Fixed effects	Multivariate	GLM
Intradeopen	-1.893 (-4.64)***	-2.175 (-5.37)***	-1.893 (-4.64)***	-1.893 (-4.64)***
lnagricexpshare	0.974 (2.45)**	0.732 (1.86)*	0.974 (2.45)**	0.974 (2.45)**
lnagricexppf	-0.386 (-1.19)	-0.167 (-0.52)	-0.386 (-1.19)	-0.386 (-1.19)
lngddpc	-0.238 (-1.40)	-0.542 (-3.07)**	-0.238 (-1.40)	-0.238 (-1.40)
goveff	-0.645 (-2.30)**	0.060 (0.19)	-0.645 (-2.30)**	-0.645 (-2.30)**
lnempagric	-1.198 (-4.54)***	-1.126 (-4.34)***	-1.198 (-4.54)***	-1.198 (-4.54)***
Constant	34.091 (14.23)***	37.496 (15.47)***	34.091 (14.23)***	34.091 (14.23)***
Wald chi2	52.32***			
F-statistics		10.57***	8.718***	
log likelihood				-2067.173
observations	748	748	748	748

Note: *** indicates 1% significance level, ** indicates 5% significance level, * indicates 10% significance level. T-statistics and Z-statistics are in parentheses. The fixed-effects model uses T-statistics whiles GLS random effects, Multivariate and GLM use Z-statistics. Model 1&2 are the main regression models and 3&4 are for robust check. All the variables are in their natural logarithm except government effectiveness.

3.6 Homogeneous causality test

The study intends to find the direction of causality between the dependent and the independent variables hence the use of homogeneous causality tests. The results of the homogeneous causality confirm evidence of both unidirectional homogeneous causality and bidirectional homogeneous causality. There is a bidirectional

homogeneous causality from the dependent variable thus agricultural growth to agricultural export performance, trade openness, employment in the agricultural sector, economic growth and government effectiveness. This direction of causality affirms that there is an inter-causal relationship between the dependent variables and the variables mentioned above. However, a change in one variable causes a change in the other variable vice versa. For instance, a change in trade openness affects agricultural growth and a change in agricultural growth affects trade openness. On the other hand, there is unidirectional homogeneous causality from agricultural growth to agricultural export share. This direction of causality signifies that agricultural growth only affects agricultural export share hence a change in agricultural growth will only affect agricultural export share but not the other way round. From all indications, it is evidenced that there is an evidence of homogeneous causality hence the rejection of the null hypothesis.

Null Hypothesis:	W-Stat.	Zbar-Stat.	Prob.	sig.
lnagexpshare does not homogeneously cause lnaggrowth	3.060	1.629	0.103	
lnaggrowth does not homogeneously cause lnagexpshare	5.817	7.593	0.000	***
lnagexppf does not homogeneously cause lnaggrowth	3.095	1.704	0.088	*
lnaggrowth does not homogeneously cause lnagexppf	5.161	6.175	0.000	***
Intradeopen does not homogeneously cause lnaggrowth	3.569	2.729	0.006	**
lnaggrowth does not homogeneously cause Intradeopen	4.439	4.612	0.000	***
lnempagric does not homogeneously cause lnaggrowth	5.180	6.215	0.000	***
lnaggrowth does not homogeneously cause lnempagric	4.183	4.057	0.000	***
lngdppc does not homogeneously cause lnaggrowth	4.872	5.549	0.000	***
lnaggrowth does not homogeneously cause lngdppc	4.841	5.482	0.000	***
goveff does not homogeneously cause lnaggrowth	3.182	1.892	0.059	**
lnaggrowth does not homogeneously cause goveff	3.454	2.480	0.013	**

Note: *** indicates 1% significance level, ** indicates 5% significance level, * indicates 10% significance level. All the variables are in their natural logarithm except government effectiveness.

4. Conclusion and recommendation

This study aimed at assessing the impact that trade liberalization has on agricultural growth in Africa and also explores the direction of the causality of the two. In line with the objective, it utilized panel study methodologies to arrive at its conclusion.

The findings of the study posit that trade liberalization and agricultural growth in Africa are inversely related; hence an increase in any of them will negatively impact the other. Moreover, in order to increase agricultural growth in Africa, then more efforts should be channeled into increasing agricultural export share; thus more agricultural produce should be exported than importing. Prospectively, more advance technologies should be included in the agricultural practices in Africa other than employing more manual labor in pursuit of higher productivity to yield growth. Perhaps, an increase in employment in the agricultural sector in the obsolete manner or means of agricultural practices have a negative or inverse relationship with agricultural growth. This implies that more human force is not needed in pursuit of agricultural growth in Africa. Therefore, governments in Africa should deploy technological means that could yield higher productivity. The study also found that governments in Africa have not been effective in formulating proactive and sound policies that could ensure higher productivity in the agricultural sectors hence increase in such efforts without devising better means to find a proper measure to curtail such issues will lead to decrease in agricultural growth.

The study recommends that governments should employ technologies that could catapult the growth in the agricultural sectors and also ensure that proper policies that could ensure delivery of public services that has a propensity to growth in the agricultural sectors. There are some limitations to the study which could stem from the sample period, econometric models and the sample countries due to their developing economies nature. In furtherance, the study recommends more research into the subject-matter with more focus on external factors

that could affect trade liberalization to impact agricultural growth to augment the discussions and policy directions in that field.

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